

CLASSIFICATION OF FRONT AND SIDE FACES WITH EDGE IMPULSE

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Summary– Estimating student engagement in the classroom is typically done by teachers through the observation of students' behaviors and facial expressions. However, identifying whether a student is engaged in a remote educational activity has posed challenges. In this article, we present a model for real-time engagement classification in virtual learning environments, utilizing the Edge Impulse tool and computer vision techniques. Data were collected from four participants, and despite challenges related to lighting conditions, the model achieved an accuracy rate of 99.2%.

Key words: Digital Education; Student Engagement; Computer vision; Edge Impulse; Real-Time Assessment.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the educational scenario has undergone a significant transformation, driven by the increasing integration of technology into the teaching-learning process. [1] The advent of digital education (E-Learning) it has brought with it a vast array of opportunities and challenges, fundamentally changing the way students interact with study materials and educators promote learning. The traditional classroom, with its blackboard and chalk, is giving way to virtual environments, where information flows in multiple directions, challenging conventional teaching methods. [2]

The spread of mobile devices such as smartphones and laptops has made it possible to access a wealth of educational resources anytime, anywhere. However, this digital revolution has brought with it a new set of challenges, especially when it comes to measuring and evaluating student engagement. How can we know if a student is truly focused and engaged in an educational activity when they are just a click away from distraction? [3]

In this context, this article aims to address this critical issue in the field of digital education. Our goal is to explore a solution that uses Edge Impulse, a machine learning platform aimed at embedded devices, in conjunction with some techniques for computer vision, to classify in real time whether a student is looking forward (indicating engagement) or to the side (indicating distraction) while participating in educational activities.[4]

Importantly, while looking ahead is a valuable indicator of engagement, truly understanding student engagement in a complex digital environment requires a more comprehensive approach. The emotion of engagement is multifaceted and intrinsically linked to the context of the learning environment.[5] Therefore, simply observing the direction of gaze is not sufficient for a complete assessment. This article focuses on exploring one of the techniques employed in this ever-evolving challenge. This is a crucial step towards a more comprehensive and accurate system for determine student engagement in digital learning environments, paving the way for future research that seeks to integrate multiple techniques and contexts for an even more accurate and holistic assessment of student engagement.[6]

DEVELOPMENT

To create an engagement classification model using Edge Impulse, essential steps are required that range from data collection to model implementation. In Fig 1, we succinctly illustrate these crucial steps, which include acquiring camera images, pre-processing the data, defining engagement classes, training the model, and finally deploying the model for evaluation. In real time.

Figure 1- Steps for Building the Model [6]

Data collection plays a crucial role in implementing the proposed system to identify student engagement and distraction during real-time educational activities. The process involved the selection of four participants representative of the target population, who voluntarily became involved in the study.

To acquire the necessary data, video recordings were made of each participant during two different sessions. In the first session, participants were positioned facing the camera, simulating an ideal state of engagement during educational activities. In the second session, they were positioned to the side, representing a possible state of distraction.

The next step consisted of extracting images from the videos, carried out at regular intervals. These images were subsequently organized into two separate sets, one for each condition (front and side), including representations of all four participants. This procedure aimed to capture natural variations in facial expressions and posture during educational activities.

The dataset used in this study consists of a total of 8,776 items. Of these, 3,503 items depict participants with their face facing forward, while 3,499 items depict participants with their face facing to the side. Once the images were organized, they were randomly divided into two distinct sets: the training set and the test set. The commonly adopted division was 80% for training and 20% for testing, although this proportion may vary according to the specific needs of the project and the size of the data set. All this data can be seen in Fig 2.

Figure 2- Selected Data

In Fig 3, you can see the unprocessed photo taken from one of the videos, which was included as 'Front_Face'.

Figure 3-Unprocessed Image

All images used in this study were standardized to a size of 96x96 pixels, as shown in Fig 4. This standardization allowed for a consistent and comparable analysis of the images, ensuring that relevant features could be adequately identified and studied.

Figure 4-Image Resizing

After configuring all these parameters, the data was prepared for training. Training was conducted over 20 cycles, representing 20 full iterations of the training dataset for learning and weight adjustment. The learning rate used was 0.0005 to control the model's learning rate. The MobileNetV2 model was used, incorporating a scale factor of 0.35. The final layer of the model consisted of 16 neurons, with a dropout rate of 0.1 for regularization. All these details can be seen in Fig 5.

Figure 5-Settings for Model Training

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After training the model, it was observed that its performance reached an accuracy rate of 99.2%, with a low loss of 0.06, as shown in Fig 6.

Figure 6- Model Accuracy

When analyzing the confusion matrix presented in Fig 7, it was observed that the model obtained an accuracy of 98.6% in classifying the class 'Face_Front' and an accuracy of 99.9% in classifying the class 'Face_Side'. However, it was identified that the model presented some difficulties in classifying frontal images, suggesting possible confusion in certain cases.

Confusion matrix (validation set)

	ROSTO_FRENTE	ROSTO_LADO
ROSTO_FRENTE	98.6%	1.4%
ROSTO_LADO	0.1%	99.9%
F1 SCORE	0.99	0.99

Figure 7- Confusion Matrix

Fig 8 illustrates an example of an error, where it is noted that the network had problems correctly discerning due to the participant's face having uneven lighting, resulting in an additional challenge for the model.

Figure 8-Image that the Model Failed

Furthermore, as part of the practical evaluation of the model, it was integrated with a cell phone camera and subjected to real-time testing. The results of these tests included presenting the 'certainty' of the model in relation to the inference at the time of screen capture. For example, in Figure 9, which represents a cell phone screenshot, we can see that the model assigned a probability of 0.92 for the presence of a face facing to the side, in contrast to only 0.08 probability for a face facing forward in that particular frame. These probabilities were represented on a scale of 0 to 1.

Inferencing...

Rosto_Lado

Time per inference: 30 ms.

	ROSTO_FRENTE	ROSTO_LADO
844	0,08	0,92
843	0,17	0,83

Figure 9- Real-Time Test with Cell Phone

The results demonstrated satisfactory performance in a real-use environment. This practical application suggests that the model can be successfully implemented in broader contexts, as part of more complex systems, to monitor student engagement. Thus, this study points to promising perspectives for future expansions and improvements in the implementation of the model for educational purposes.

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